

Reflectance properties of North West Africa 13951 and 16372. C. Carli¹, F.Tosi¹, F.-E. Jadid², and H. Chennaoui², ¹IAPS-INAf (via del Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Roma, Italy; cristian.carli@inaf.it), ²GAIA Laboratory, Hassan II University of Casablanca, Faculty of Science Ain Chock, Morocco.

Introduction: Lunar meteorites have been increasing in number, in particular from hot desert (e.g. [1]) in the last years. These rocks can be accessible to researchers, opening the possibility to study different lithologies contributing to the lunar crust, not necessarily sampled by the Apollo missions' landing sites and more recent robotic landing sites (e.g. Chang'e 5). One technique that allows to investigate the main mineralogy with minor sample preparation, is reflectance spectroscopy. In the visible and near-infrared (VNIR) spectral range, the reflectance of the Moon has been investigated by different spacecraft. For instance, in the 90s, the Clementine mission was equipped by ultraviolet to visible (UV-VIS) and NIR cameras, producing the first maps of mineral phases (e.g. Plagioclase Pl, Pyroxene Px, Olivine Ol), some retrieved oxide composition (i.e. FeO and TiO₂), and maps related to space weathering (nFe⁰) (e.g. [2]). More recently, SP onboard SELENE, M3 onboard Chandrayaan-1, IIM onboard Chang-e 1, and IIRS onboard Chandrayaan-2, characterised the lunar surface with hyperspectral data defining e.g. pure anorthite regions PAN [3], olivine-enriched outcrops (e.g. [4,5]), detecting Mg-spinel enriched lithologies [6], or discussing the stratigraphy and so the evolution of Basins (e.g. [7]). Here we report spectral properties of two peculiar lunar meteorites: NWA 13951 and NWA 16372, following the same approach in [8,9,10].

Methods and Analytical approach: The investigation of hyperspectral reflectance data analysis is continuously under development with more evolved techniques with the aim to improve the information we can obtain from those remotely sensed data. To support this investigation, laboratory systematic datasets can be used as test, where to compare more traditional data analysis, retrieving specific absorption parameters, the mineral-chemical and petrographic information, with hyperspectral data analysis. Here we acquired several reflectance punctual measurements on different portions of the samples. Moreover, systematic transect or matrix of punctual acquisition, oversampling the spot sizes, to simulate different areal mixing from clast and matrix or between two contiguous clasts were performed. We preliminarily defined spectral parameters from single spots to investigate their variation among the areal mixtures. We will investigate then Transect and Matrix with hyperspectral and clustering techniques.

Data set: Meteorite spectra were measured using the Fieldspec Pro spectrophotometer mounted on

the goniometer present at the S.LAB. laboratory at INAF-IAPS, Rome. The data cover the spectral range 0.35–2.50 μm with a spectral resolution from 3 nm in the VIS and 10 nm in the NIR, at fixed illumination and viewing angles of 30° and 0°, respectively. The source was a QTH lamp and the spot illuminated had a diameter of about 6 mm. The standard reference calibration was performed with a Spectralon optical standard 99%. Spectra are an average of 200 acquisitions. Transect spectra are acquired with 0.5 mm shift from one point to the following, whereas Matrix spectra are acquired with 2 mm steps along the Y axis and 4 mm steps along the X axis.

Samples: NWA 13951 is a very fine-grained Lunar feldspathic breccia with a main mineral assemblage of pl, px, ol, and a large portion of melt [11]. They identified. Moreover, numerous Fe-Ni metal grains are scattered throughout. NWA 16372 is a Lunar meteorite defined as a brecciated troctolitic anorthosite with high abundance of pl (~90%), and low amount of ol (~5%), and High-Ca px (~1%) plus minor other components [12].

For both of them we studied the reflectance properties of slices which were polished to avoid the asperities left by the saw. NWA 13951 size is circa 5*5 cm and NWA 16372 size is circa 7*7 cm.

Preliminary Results: Meteorite reflectance spectra show very low alteration processes with almost no water/OH⁻ related overtone.

Both samples show brecciated structures even if with different clast distribution and dimensions, as well as a different relative amount of the fine-grained groundmass. This has an impact in the spectral variability within a spot of circa 6 mm since different clasts, if attributable to different mineralogy, will show a higher spectral variability where they are bigger, with lower fine-groundmass abundance, with respect to the samples where they are in dimension smaller than the illuminated spot.

NWA 13951 shows lower spectral variability with a variation in reflectance from clasts to the ground mass, and absorptions around 950 and 1950 (weaker) nm, with very small position shifts. The transect (Figure 1) from the bigger (1 cm²) and brighter clast shows as some variability could be highlighted also in the convexity in the spectral range 500-750 nm and the shift of the reflectance maximum from 500 up to 420 nm.

NWA 16372 shows a higher spectral variability, due to the presence of more heterogeneous clasts. Reflectance varies within 0.05-0.22, relatively dark

Figure 1 – Reflectance spectra from the larger clast (brighter) up to the surrounding ground mass

with respect to the average values of 90% of pl detected in the sample. Spectra show a prominent absorption around 1000 nm and a weaker absorption around 2000 nm, not always present.

The first absorptions show a noticeable shift from about 960 nm up to 1060 nm. When the band is shifted to longer wavelengths, its right shoulder shifts up to 1700 nm absorption and 2000 nm absorption is absent.

Band positions are consistent with pyroxene (augite) and olivine composition. Conversely, plagioclase is not easily detected, despite a changing in spectral asymmetry from 1100 nm and 1600 nm. Future investigation will clarify if this attributable to plagioclase rather than variable olivine contents. The visible range shows a spectral variability correlated with the main absorptions, and in particular some spectra show weak absorptions at 505 and 550 nm attributed to spin forbidden transitions [e.g. 13]. Interesting is also the comparison of the different behaviour of the two samples in the visible since both samples have the same type of surfaces, with a possible implication to mineral-chemistry reason, which has to be further investigated.

Figure 2 - Reflectance spectra from different portions of the samples, reflectance is shifted for figure clarity.

Implications: The spectral variability of this two meteorites highlight the importance of detailed spectra investigation of lunar samples not only as particulate, to maximise and better understand the

capability to detect and discern the mineralogical information from remotely sensed data. Highlands-like material, such as the feldspathic breccia and anorthositic troctolite treated here, have relatively low reflectance and spectra mainly dominated by a mafic mineralogy, similar to what reported in [7,8]. This is an important aspect to be taken into account during the spectral interpretation of mafic regions within Highlands crater and the relative proportion of plagioclase vs mafic minerals.

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